

Psychological and Economic Dimensions of Gig Economy and Freelancing: Challenges and Opportunities in Modern Working Models

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ABSTRACT : This article aims to comprehensively examine the psychological and economic effects of the gig economy and freelancing on modern working patterns. While the gig economy refers to a working model that generates income through short-term, independent jobs and projects, freelancing covers a broader form of independent work. The article analyzes the implications of these two working models on both individuals and the general economy.

The gig economy and freelancing have significant effects on individuals' psychological states. Research shows that these ways of working offer high flexibility and independence, but also bring challenges such as uncertainty, low income security and social isolation. Key factors affecting psychological health include lack of job security, constant pressure to perform, and lack of social connection. This study examines how individuals cope with these psychological challenges and how they affect their quality of life. The gig economy and freelancing models present both economic opportunities and risks. Economic opportunities include faster entry into the job market, reduced costs, and access to a broader customer base. However, these models also carry risks such as economic uncertainties and lack of social protections such as health insurance and retirement plans. The article evaluates these economic elements and analyzes the financial challenges faced by freelancers and gig economy workers.

As a result, while the gig economy and freelancing bring flexibility and independence to the modern workforce, they also create a variety of psychological and economic challenges. This study provides recommendations to minimize these challenges and maximize opportunities. In particular, it is emphasized that supportive social policies, psychological support programs and financial security systems should be developed.

KEYWORDS: Gig economy, freelancing, psychological effects, economic aspects, modern working patterns, job security, uncertainty, flexibility and independence, social security, performance pressure, income security, social isolation, financial risks, financial security, psychological support programs.

INTRODUCTION

Over the last few decades, there have been radical changes in the labor market. At the center of these changes is the rise of new working models such as the gig economy and freelancing. Technological developments, the spread of digital platforms and globalization have increased flexibility and diversity in ways of doing business, enabling alternative ways of working beyond the traditional 9-5 work order. While the gig economy refers to short-term projects and tasks that rely on independent labor, freelancing encompasses a broader form of independent work. These new working patterns present significant opportunities and challenges for both individuals and companies.

The gig economy can be defined as a business model in which individuals earn income through short-term, project-based jobs and tasks. In this model, jobs are often found through digital platforms and jobs can have short durations. For example, Uber driving, freelance software development and graphic design are examples of this model. Freelancing, on the other hand, refers to a situation where individuals start their own business or work independently on various projects. In this model, individuals generally have the freedom to set their own work hours and manage projects directly with their clients.

While the gig economy and freelancing present risks such as lack of job security and a steady stream of income, they also offer a high degree of flexibility and independence. This situation can have significant effects on individuals' psychological health. Psychologically, uncertainty and low income security can increase levels of stress and anxiety; High flexibility and independence can increase life satisfaction and job satisfaction. Therefore, understanding the effects of the gig economy and freelancing models on individuals' mental health is critical to making these forms of work more sustainable and supportive.

From an economic perspective, the gig economy and freelancing present a variety of opportunities and risks for both individuals and companies. While for individuals, these work models can provide more job opportunities and sources of income, they can also present challenges such as lack of social protections (e.g. health insurance, retirement funds). For companies, these models offer advantages such as reducing costs, flexible workforce management and access to a wide talent pool. However, in addition to these advantages, problems such as job insecurity and employee commitment may also arise.

This study aims to understand the opportunities and challenges faced by these new working patterns by examining both the psychological and economic aspects of the gig economy and freelancing. The research will evaluate the psychological effects and economic consequences of these working styles on individuals and make recommendations for the implementation of these models in a healthier and more sustainable way. Additionally, this study aims to better manage the social and economic impacts of these new working patterns by providing information for policy makers, employers and freelancers.

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AIM

The main purpose of this study is to comprehensively examine the psychological and economic effects of the gig economy and freelancing on modern workforce dynamics. In particular, this study pursues the following main objectives:

Analysis of Psychological Effects: To discuss in detail the effects of the gig economy and freelancing on individuals' psychological health. In this context, to investigate the effects of factors such as lack of job security, income uncertainty, social isolation and performance pressure on stress, anxiety and life satisfaction. Additionally, to evaluate the positive effects of positive factors such as flexibility and independence on individuals' mental health.

Evaluation of Economic Results: This study aims to analyze the economic aspects of the gig economy and freelancing models, revealing the opportunities and risks faced by individuals and companies. In this context, to examine economic factors such as flexibility in the labor market, cost advantages, income diversity and lack of social security. Additionally, to evaluate the economic impacts of financial uncertainties faced by freelancers and lack of social security such as health insurance and retirement.

Suggestions for Improving Working Conditions: Another aim of the research is to develop applicable strategies and policies to minimize the difficulties and maximize the opportunities brought by the gig economy and freelancing. In this context, to offer suggestions on how social policies, psychological support programs and financial security systems can be improved. Aiming to create a more sustainable and supportive working environment by addressing problems such as job insecurity and lack of social support.

Providing Information for Policymakers and Employers: This study aims to provide information and data for policymakers and employers to help them understand the impacts of the gig economy and freelancing. This data will form the basis for developing workforce policies, enabling employers to work more effectively with freelancers, and adopting more fair and inclusive practices in the labor market.

Directing Future Research: The findings of the study will be used to lay the groundwork for future research on the gig economy and freelancing. In this context, it is aimed to identify potential research areas to expand and deepen the subject of the study, to contribute to the literature and to fill the knowledge gaps in this field of study.

METHOD

In this study, the literature review method was applied. This method used aims to examine the multidimensional effects of the flexible economy and freelance work in more detail. During the literature review, findings from previous research addressing the psychological and economic consequences of the gig economy and freelancing were taken into account. These studies analyzed the validity and reliability of various questionnaires and scales; identified tools used to measure elements such as job insecurity, income uncertainty, stress, anxiety and quality of life. For example, Kuhn and Maleki (2017) conducted a study investigating the effects of the gig economy on stress and anxiety. Additionally, Brewster et al. (2020) examined the implications of freelance working conditions on economic security and job satisfaction. The findings of these studies formed an important basis in the design of existing surveys and scales. The literature review also explored existing methods of how in-depth interviews and case studies are conducted. In particular, Kalleberg (2018) and Graham et al. (2017) have detailed qualitative research methods used to understand the experiences of individuals in the gig economy. This literature has provided valuable information about qualitative data collection techniques and thematic analysis methods and created a framework for how to apply these techniques.

RESULTS

A. Conceptual Structure on Remote Working

Remote working began to reach large audiences in line with the demands of organizations before the 1990s. Today, the effectiveness of remote working has increased thanks to the support of elements such as work life balance (Irawanto, Novianti, Roz, 2021, 1-2). In this context, remote working has become a concept that expresses a modern working order shaped by information and communication technologies. Remote working is defined as a method that allows employees to carry out business activities outside corporate areas (Al-Rfou, 2021, 96). This practice can be summarized as it offers employees the opportunity to work beyond traditional office environments.

Current research reveals the positive and negative effects of remote working on both employees and employers. For example, some studies show that remote working has an impact on employees' psychological health, affecting their job satisfaction and performance management. For employers, improvements are observed in employee retention, while employees are provided with appropriate opportunities to achieve work-life balance and fulfill their job descriptions; In social terms, environmental benefits and reduction of carbon footprint create positive economic and social results (Beno, 2021, 11-12).

Another study emphasizes that the remote working method creates a win-win situation for both employers and employees. For employers, positive aspects such as less use of office spaces, providing a better work-life balance for employees, increasing job satisfaction and strengthening organizational commitment come to the fore (Felstad, Henseke, 2017, 197). Another published study states that remote working has advantages such as making it easier for employers to reach potential employees, reducing office expenses, saving employees in terms of time and costs spent commuting to work, being able to spend more time with their families, and making it easier to find a job in other cities. This situation reveals the positive aspects of remote working for both employers and employees (Blumberga, Pylinskaya, 2019, 277). The advantages and disadvantages of remote working across research are summarized below (Ferreira, Pereira, Bianchi, Da Silva, 2021, 6-7).

Advantages and disadvantages of remote working:

Advantages of remote working

✓ Autonomy provided for employees

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- ✓ Accelerated development
- ✓ Increased accessibility
- ✓ High employee productivity
- ✓ Reducing burnout levels

Disadvantages of remote working

- ✓ The employee feels lonely
- ✓ Increased workload
- ✓ Dividing the work into specific situations
- ✓ Delay in resolving complexities
- ✓ Difficulties with time management

B. Analysis of Remote Working During COVID-19

There have been many changes in working methods from past to present. One of these changes is the transition of employees to a remote working model. Remote working has become a slowly but steadily becoming widespread working style. The rate of remote working in Europe has increased over the years, from 5.4% to 9%. The COVID-19 period has created a significant impact that accelerated this proportional increase. This rapid change in working styles has brought about problems such as employees being caught unprepared and lack of experience (Tramontano, Grant, Clarke, 2021, 1).

Besides this, there are other factors that contribute to the problems that arise. For example, studies conducted in several countries have shown that in the United States, job losses are three times higher for jobs that do not allow telecommuting than for jobs that do accommodate telecommuting. Factors affecting job losses include gender, ethnic group and education level. According to research in Italy, it has been observed that the inequalities existing in the labor markets have become even more evident with remote working. It has been concluded that highly educated and highly paid employees benefit from remote working opportunities more than other employees (Depalo, 2021, 5-6).

Research on remote working during the COVID-19 period shows that high-income workers have an advantage in diversifying their workplace opportunities and obtaining work equipment. Additionally, differences were observed in the role perceptions and expectations of female employees compared to male employees. The role played by other family members in the remote working process and the difficulty of finding a suitable workspace are among the difficulties brought by this system (Al-Rfou, 2021, 99-101). Remote working has also caused various challenges in team functions. For example, the opportunity to get instant help among team members was lost and there were disruptions in the processes of cooperation and connection (Cook, Zschomler, Biggart, Carder, 2020, 263-264).

The COVID-19 period has led to the introduction of various applications into the lives of employees that can reduce the difficulties of remote working. For example, digital collaborations in sectors suitable for remote work have been continued through digital platforms. It is seen that efficiency and effectiveness in the applied business areas show a significant increase compared to before COVID-19 (Gupta, 2020, 1-2). The high rate of this increase is due to the greater efficiency and effectiveness obtained from remote working, especially in societies with higher education levels and richer and denser populations; This situation also plays a catalytic role in the transition to a remote working system (Crowley, Doran, 2020, 1225). Studies on remote working during the COVID-19 period are presented below.

Wang, Liu, Qian, Parker (2021): This study identified four challenges each regarding remote working and virtual work features. The research found that social support has a positive relationship with remote working difficulties, disruption of work schedule is linked to workload, and a negative correlation between autonomy in doing work and feeling lonely.

Gallacher, Hossain (2020): According to a study conducted in Canada, 41% of the society started to work remotely during the COVID-19 period. It was observed that the transition to remote working system in March and April 2020 did not cause job losses at the lowest rates. It has been concluded that remote working opportunities are limited for insufficient education levels, seasonal and part-time employees, non-immigrant employees and young individuals.

Brynjolfsson, Horton, Ozimek, Rock, Sharma, TuYe (2020): With the beginning of the COVID-19 period in America, layoffs and long-term work leaves affected 10.1% of the society. The study found a negative relationship between working from home and going to work. It has been observed that it is easier for young individuals, management level employees and professional workforce to transition to the remote working system. It has been determined that employees defined as knowledge workers tend to leave work less frequently and take longer breaks from work.

Gómez, Mendoza, Ramírez, Olivas-Luján (2020): With the beginning of the pandemic, it has been observed that the stress caused by COVID-19 in business environments in Mexico has an impact on the workforce. According to the results of the research, it has been determined that the workload on individuals increases with remote working.

Angelucci, Angrisani, Bennett, Kapteyn, Schaner (2020): According to a study conducted in America, it was found that the job losses of those who were not suitable for remote work were three times higher than those who were suitable. It has been observed that job losses were experienced at the highest rate among female employees, and Hispanics, African-Americans and employees without a degree were also included in this group. It has been determined that those who are not suitable for remote work are more likely to suffer from respiratory diseases due to their low ability to protect themselves, and the highest loss of life occurs in this group.

Béland, Brodeur, Wright (2020): According to a study conducted in America, employees in occupational groups suitable for remote work were less affected by this working order than those who were not suitable. In the study, suggestions were made for the development of infrastructure and institutional policies that will support remote working.

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Beland, Brodeur, Haddad, Mikola (2020): In a study conducted in Canada, it was found that remote working practices were not effective on stress formations in the family.

Molino, Ingusci, Signore, Manuti, Giancaspro, Russo, Cortese (2020): In a study conducted in Italy, it was determined that remote working creates "techno stress". A positive relationship was found between techno-stress and workload, family turmoil and individual stress.

Van Zoonen, Sivunen, Blomqvist, Olsson, Ropponen, Henttonen, Vartiainen (2021): Research shows that structural factors make remote working easier for employees. It has been determined that the most important variable affecting remote working is social isolation.

Dubey, Tripathi, (2020): According to the study, the concept of working from home was perceived positively by individuals. The existence of trust and expectation variables was cited as the reason for its welcome. According to the research, 100,000 tweets on Twitter were examined and word clouds associated with remote working were created. These; The words "good", "break", "hope", "love", "sharing", "happiness", "safety", "home", "team", "management", "fun", "trust" were detected in frequently written tweets. The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly changed today's working conditions and types of work. The pandemic has also led to transformations in organizational working models, causing institutions to make various adaptations in their employees' working concepts. In addition to providing an alternative for organizations, remote working has also led to the emergence of different models. Models for remote working are presented below (Achurch Consulting, 2021).

- Remote working model that does not exist in the same time zone (Fully RemoteAsynchronous):

Features

- ✓ The institution does not have a physical office.
- ✓ Remote working method has been adopted.
- ✓ No time restrictions for communication and business processes.
- ✓ Employees only come together for meetings.
- ✓ Employees can reside anywhere in the world.

Opportunities

- ✓ Flexible working opportunity for employees.
- ✓ The advantage of being able to provide programs with continuous employee or customer service at any time period.
- ✓ Employers can set salaries according to the standards of the country where the employees are located.

- Remote working model applied in the same time period (Fully RemoteSynchronous):

Features

- ✓ Obligation to work within certain hours determined by the institution.
- ✓ Employees are required to be in the same geographical areas.

Opportunities

- ✓ Ease of communication is provided for employees.
- ✓ Organizing one-on-one meetings includes the ability for all employees to participate.

- Hybrid model (Hybrid model):

Features

- ✓ Some of the employees are present in the office.
- ✓ Other employees have the option to participate remotely or from home.
- ✓ The environment in which employees work (office or home) is clearly determined.

Opportunities

- ✓ Contributing to the reduction of operational costs.
- ✓ Providing a wide range of choices for potential employees to be employed.

- Partially Remote Work model:

Features

- ✓ The majority, but not all, of employees have the opportunity to work from the office or from home for a few days.

Opportunities

- ✓ Facilitating coordination between teams
- ✓ Reduction of operational costs

- Remote work focused model (Remote-First Work):

Features

- ✓ The majority of employees work remotely.
- ✓ The main purpose is the remote working model.
- ✓ The number of employees in the office is quite low.
- ✓ There is the opportunity to come to the office only for meetings or operational requirements.

Opportunities

- ✓ Flexibility in working conditions

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- ✓ Reduction in office expenses
- ✓ Supporting work-life balance
- Work-oriented model from the office (Office-First Work):

Features

- ✓ It is essential that the majority of employees work from the office.
- ✓ Offering the opportunity to work remotely once a week or once a month.

Opportunities

- ✓ Facilitating the integration of employees
- ✓ Instant one-on-one meeting opportunity
- ✓ Possibility to provide instant solutions to problems

C. Conceptual Framework Addressing Work-Life Balance.

Although the concept of work-life balance emerged in the 1930s, its widespread use began in the 1970s in England and in the 1980s in America, and then became known worldwide. The concept, which first developed in these countries, was shaped by the institutional adaptation of work life programs specifically aimed at supporting female employees. Thus, definitions have been developed so that employees can establish balance in their family and professional lives and harmonize their work and personal activities with the determined priorities (Ramakrishnan, 2020, 3-4).

Studies emphasize the importance of employees establishing a successful balance between the roles required by the job and the roles in their private lives (Uddin, 2021, 2). Some other studies focus on the balance between the time allocated to business life and the time allocated to private life (Wolor, Solikhah, Fidhyallah, Lestari, 2020, 445). Research offers various definitions and models to understand work life balance.

Achieving work life balance successfully is possible by reducing the effects of factors (time, limitations, behaviors) that may have a negative impact. This model has a structure that brings together work-life conflict and work-life enrichment. In the model, the factors that negatively affect work life balance are defined as role inequalities, while the elements that can have a positive impact are shown through role interviews. It has been demonstrated that work life balance can be achieved more effectively if the factors contributing to work life enrichment are increased (McMillan, 2011, 15-16).

D. Evaluation of Work and Life Balance During Covid-19

Work-life balance, which was widely studied before the pandemic, is being researched more with the increase in affecting variables in the post-pandemic period. When this issue, which has been on the agenda for more than 20 years, is evaluated from the perspective of remote working, flexible working practices give individuals the authority to decide when and where they will work, causing them to gain more autonomy in ensuring their work-life balance (Anderson, Kelliher, 2020, 678). This autonomy allows employees to maintain their work life balance with individual schedules. In this context, research has been conducted that offers various suggestions to help employees maintain their work-life balance. One of these studies focused on eight important factors to achieve balance. These factors include factors such as stress management, adequate sleep patterns, maintaining physical activities, paying attention to healthy nutrition, individual rewards increasing motivation, turning to activities that improve fighting skills, creating a positive individual identity and organizing time well (Amin, Griffiths, Dsouza)., 2020, 2). In other studies, recommendations vary. According to a study conducted in Georgia, various recommendations were offered to both institutions and individuals to maintain work-life balance. For example, human resources management should guide employees to maintain a balanced work-life, increase communication between employees, not coincide with online meetings on days off, human resources managers develop strategies, review organizational culture, implement hybrid working models and adapt offices to the digitalization process. is among the recommendations (Gigauri, 2020).

E. Research on Work Life Balance During Covid-19

Alfanza (2021): A study conducted in the Philippines found a negative relationship between employees' work life balance and remote working. This shows that remote working negatively affects work life balance. Additionally, it was concluded that there is no difference between job completion rate and job completion time in remote working and office working situations.

Campo, Avolio, Carlier (2021): This study found no correlation between remote work and job performance or work life balance. However, it was concluded that there was a positive relationship between job performance and family supportive behaviors and work life balance.

Gigauri (2020): In the study, it was determined that employees doing work late and including weekends in their working hours is a factor that negatively affects work life balance. This situation has revealed that the lack of distinction between work and private life leads to increased stress in individuals.

Irawanto, Novianti, Roz (2021): A study of employees in Indonesia showed that remote working had a negative impact on work life balance and job stress on job satisfaction.

Pai, Patil, Kamath, Mahendra, Singhal, Bhat (2021): In a study conducted with dentists in India, it was concluded that physical and mental activities, social relations and the working environment have a direct impact on the work life balance of employees and that work life imbalance It has been determined that it is most common in female dentists.

Putri, Amran (2021): A study conducted in Indonesia revealed that remote working has a significant and positive impact on work life balance.

Kumar, Mokashi (2020): In this research, supervisor support and proactive work behavior of employees are the factors used to explain work life balance. It has been determined that there is a strong connection between employees' proactive work behaviors

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and work life balance. Consultant support helps employees maintain work life balance effectively by increasing their proactive behavior.

Vinberg, Danielsson (2020): In a study conducted with managers working in small-scale businesses in Switzerland, it was observed that the pandemic negatively affected work-life balance.

Yerkes, André, Remery, Salin, Hakovirta, Gerven (2020): A study conducted in Finland and the Netherlands revealed that Finnish mothers have more difficulties in maintaining work-life balance than Dutch mothers. The reason for this is that most Dutch mothers work part-time, while Finnish mothers are mostly employed full-time.

Wan Mohd Yunus, Badri, Panatik, Mukhtar (2021): A study conducted with university students in Malaysia revealed that restrictions during the Covid-19 period had a negative impact on students' work life balance and happiness levels.

Various alternatives are offered to help employees maintain their work life balance during Covid-19. These alternatives provide guidance on actions that both organizations and individuals can take.

F. The Effects of Remote Working and Work-Life Balance on Employee Motivation

Among the factors affecting employee motivation, there are two main factors that stand out during the Covid-19 period: remote working and work-life balance. One of the effects of remote working on motivation is providing an open communication environment. In this context, leaders appear to play a critical role. Supporting employees, providing guidance such as guidance and coaching, preventing communication breakdowns and granting autonomy to employees are among the factors that increase motivation (Virtanen, 2020, pp. 9-12). In addition, meeting the basic psychological needs (autonomy, competitiveness) of employees in remote working arrangements also affects motivation (Orsini, Rodrigues, 2020, p. 1).

The effects of work-life balance on employee motivation are manifested by observing improvements in productivity, quality time spent with family and work performance when this balance is achieved (MBASKool Team, 2021). In summary, in addition to many factors affecting employee motivation, the importance of remote working and work-life balance during the pandemic period draws attention. The increase in the positive aspects of remote working and the positive elements that can be achieved in work-life balance are considered as factors that constantly increase motivation. Therefore, if leaders within the organization take the necessary steps on these issues during the pandemic period, it will both increase employee motivation and strengthen the competitiveness of the organization against other organizations.

G. Some Suggestions for Achieving Work-Life Balance

Recommendations for organizations: Encouraging employees to take annual leave

Conclusions: Although working from home is not a holiday, it will increase employee motivation.

Recommendations for employees: Setting physical boundaries

Conclusions: It is important to create a different area for the office layout.

Recommendations for organizations: Promoting flexibility

Conclusions: Making time for activities outside of work is beneficial in maintaining balance.

Recommendations for employees: Setting mental boundaries

Results: Frees up time to focus on non-work activities.

Recommendations for organizations: Regular review of work by the organization

Results: Increasing control over employees helps them focus better on their work.

Recommendations for employees: Being transparent to inform employers about their projects

Results: Helps employers be more effective in resolving situations faced by employees.

Recommendations for organizations: Accepting the individual differences of employees

Results: Providing various opportunities for remote working increases employee motivation.

Recommendations for employees: The feeling of being constantly busy with work should be avoided.

Results: Helps reduce having to perform tasks all the time during activities outside of work.

H. Effects of Remote Working and Work-Life Balance on Employee Motivation

Grant, Wallace, Spurgeon (2013): Access to technology and flexible working conditions play an effective role on motivation.

Morganson, Major, Oborn, Verive, Heelan (2010): It positively affects job satisfaction by increasing employee motivation.

Zamani, Hanafi, Ghani, Radzi, Rahmat, Kadar, Azram (2021): The flexibility offered in the work environment positively affects employee motivation by increasing work performance with the shortening of travel time from home to work or from work to home.

CONCLUSION

Today, the emergence of the Covid-19 virus has led to societies around the world entering into closure processes. During this period of closure, various changes took place in people's lives, and these changes began to affect many areas of life. For organizations, it has become necessary to make changes in workflow systems, review of policies regarding working models, and make permanent or temporary arrangements depending on the development of the pandemic. The rapid spread of the virus at the beginning of the pandemic resulted in the first precaution taken by institutions to protect their employees by switching from office working to working from home. Changes began to be made in business processes and the measures taken accelerated the transition to the period called "new normal". As working environments moved from the office to the home, technological tools and applications became more involved in the lives of employees and began to be widely used to carry out work. In this process, organizations have mobilized all their resources to develop the technological infrastructure, determine the needs of employees and adapt to the new order. The different ways of working brought by the new normal have revealed both positive and negative aspects in the lives of employees. Remote working has played an important role in increasing productivity and providing flexibility (Hermann, Paris, 2020, 329).

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However, in addition to the positive aspects of this situation, some negative effects have also been observed. Perceived stress levels and burnout, especially among the challenges of remote working, have caused changes in the psychological states of employees. It has been found that employees with work arrangements that are not suitable for remote work experience higher levels of stress compared to others (Hayes, Priestley, Ray, Lishmakhametov, 2020, 17). In addition, negative effects of remote working have been observed in employees who do not have sufficient technological infrastructure or who integrate low levels of technology into their work routines. Time management problems, accessibility problems in communication networks, disruptions in collaboration, and the lack of experience that most employees experience in adapting to the new normal reflect the negative aspects of remote working. The progression and rapid spread of the pandemic period has led to greater integration of business life into family lives. It is observed that the boundaries between employees' work life and private life are becoming increasingly blurred. This situation has caused the responsibilities of fulfilling the requirements of business life to shift from the office environment to the home environment. In addition to the positive aspects that emerge, negative effects are also felt. Factors that contribute positively to work-life balance include the reduction in transportation costs, the elimination of time spent going to work, encouraging employees and institutions to use advanced technological tools, providing flexibility, the ability of individuals to create their own programs instead of dependence on corporate programs, and increasing individual autonomy. However, there are also factors that negatively affect work-life balance. For example, negative effects arise such as the difficulty of striking a balance between work time and quality time spent with family, difficulties experienced by employees in reaching people with whom they can quickly find solutions when they encounter work-related problems, and difficulties in accessing resources suitable for office work in the home environment.

All these situations reveal the effects of the remote working model and ensuring work-life balance on employee motivation. The narrowing of the communication network caused by remote working, meetings held at certain times, not being able to provide instant feedback and not being able to provide timely information about business life are important factors affecting employee motivation. In addition, difficulties in maintaining work-life balance can negatively affect employees' motivation. Decreases in productivity, job performance and job satisfaction, combined with increases in stress levels, damage employees' motivation and cause their fulfillment needs to not be met. It is observed that an employee with low motivation has problems both in achieving the goals of the organization and in achieving individual career goals.

Therefore, the negative and positive effects of remote working and work-life balance on employee motivation are felt by both institutions and employees during the Covid-19 pandemic period. Minimizing negative impacts requires the responsibilities of both institutions and employees. Institutions should help employees achieve their goals, provide the necessary technological infrastructures, and support employees in managing their family and work lives in a balanced manner. In order for employees to reduce the negative effects of remote working and work-life balance, it is important to allocate time for non-work activities, set limits on working hours, and embody the necessary elements in their lives so that they do not feel obliged to constantly engage in activities outside of work.

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